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Clock synchronicity experiment

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1 Intro

Since I've been experiencing increased synchronicity lately regarding clocks and observed time I decided to run an experiment for a couple of days to quantify the effect.

2 The hypothesis

I hypothesize that the distribution of observed times on a microwave clock will not be random, the minutes in time observed will be clumped about specific peaks, these peaks being the numbers I encounter most often in synchronicity events:

22, 23, 33, 43

The choice of the microwave clock for the experiment does not imply that this synchronicity is limited to that specific clock (it should be clock-agnostic).

This particular clock was chosen in order to minimize the *noise* (i.e., accidental looks at the clock). In example, a clock shown on a computer monitor attracts attention during computer usage and it would be harder to distinguish between deliberate and accidental looks.

3 Methodology

From my experience, synchronicity is deeply correlated with subconsciousness. Therefore, in the experiment, any conscious look at the clock will be disregarded.

What will be noted is time at any deliberate but subconsciously initiated look at the clock. Here "deliberate" means the look cannot be interpreted as forced or accidental. In example, it can be hard to avoid looking at the clock when one is walking towards it - this is generally not deliberate (although not necessarily), rather forced, even if not conscious. On the other hand, lying in bed watching television and then suddenly rotating the head 90 degrees to focus on the microwave clock for a moment is not accidental, it is deliberate, but does not have to be conscious.

However, there are different levels of subconsciousness and sometimes it may be hard to say whether the action was completely conscious or subconscious. The action may be a superposition of both and such cases will be noted too.

The deeper correlation of synchronicity with subconsciousness rather than consciousness suggests that deviation from the hypothesized peaks may be proportional to the amount of consciousness involved in action. This will be tested too.

4 Results

Results of the experiment are shown in Table 1.

	date	observed time	subconscious action [%]	subconscious action, expected [%]
1.	2023.03.12	03:33	100	100.00
2.	2023.03.12	15:22	100	100.00
3.	2023.03.12	18:22	100	100.00
4.	2023.03.12	21:22	100	100.00
5.	2023.03.14	03:23	100	100.00
6.	2023.03.14	13:32	50	96. $\bar{6}$
7.	2023.03.15	00:43	100	100.00
8.	2023.03.15	02:44	50	96. $\bar{6}$
9.	2023.03.15	22:44	50	96. $\bar{6}$

Table 1: Clock synchronicity

Here "subconscious action" is my rough approximation of the amount of subconsciousness in the intent to look at the clock. Expected subconscious action represents the calculated inverse of deviation of minutes in measured time from the nearest peak:

$$s = \frac{30 - d}{30} 100 [\%]$$

where d is the distance of measured minutes to the nearest peak.

It should be noted that, although *completely* (dominantly) conscious looks at the clock are not included in Table 1, measured minutes occasionally included hypothesized peaks even in these, more often than it would be expected for random distribution.

5 Discussion

When it comes to experiments of this kind the primary question is: for how long the experiment should run (or how big the sample size should be) in order for confidence to be high enough to rule out coincidence?

Certainly, one cannot expect to experience this kind of synchronicity indefinitely and, according to my theories, amount of synchronicity should oscillate or fluctuate. Therefore, occasional clumping of synchronicity events is expected. Clumping can occur in random distribution as well but there it is usually an illusion stemming from cognitive bias or small sample size. Here, however, it is hard to argue for randomness (note that the similar high *microwave-clock-synchronicity* was present even before the experiment and continued after it).

From the start of the experiment, 5 times in a row the numbers were among the hypothesized peaks, the odds for this happening at random are:

$$\left(\frac{4}{60}\right)^5 = \left(\frac{1}{15}\right)^5 = 1.317 \times 10^{-6} = 1 : 759\,375$$

But not all peaks were observed (one of them repeated 3 times, the other two were unique) so the odds for this combination are even lower:

$$1 : 3\,200\,000$$

This alone strongly suggests that distribution of subconscious looks at the clock here was not random.

Taking everything into account, the odds for the outcome of the experiment (6 peaks out of 9 measurements) to be a product of chance are:

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{n}{k} \times (60 - 4)^{n-k} \times \frac{1}{60^n} &= \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!} \times (60 - 4)^{n-k} \times \frac{1}{60^n} \\ &= 84 \times 56^3 \times \frac{1}{60^9} = 1.463801 \times 10^{-9} \\ &= 1 : 683\,152\,853 \end{aligned}$$

$$n = \text{total number of measurements} = 9$$

$$k = \text{number of observed peaks} = 6$$

All times observed through 100% subconscious action contain the hypothesized peaks and even those less subconscious are only 60 seconds (or less) away from the peak.

Interestingly, even hours in observed times don't seem to be random. In all cases of 100% subconscious action they are multiples of number 3 while in all cases of less subconscious action they are not - suggesting cyclic expression of subconscious correlation.

There are different interpretations, or possible mechanisms involved in this synchronicity.

From my experience, synchronicity usually requires effective subconscious precognition. In this particular case, however, this is not required but may be explained by the correlation of an internal (i.e., biological) clock with the physical clock and deliberate action of subconsciousness at specific intervals (times) effectively measured internally. I propose that the amount and quality of information transfer between consciousness and subconsciousness depends on the individual (particularly on [sub]species[1]). Our consciousness cannot directly measure time of the internal clock but, at some level, subconsciousness has access to it. In this case, the individual consciously wanted to measure synchronicity. It is possible that here, due to deeper correlation or mutual understanding (cooperation or symbiosis) between different levels of consciousness, the subconsciousness itself decided to cooperate and make the wish of the individual's consciousness come true.

However, synchronicity was present even before the conscious start of the experiment. This suggests that, subconsciously, either the experiment started earlier or subconsciousness stimulated conscious experimentation by precursor synchronicity.

Note that *my* synchronicity events involving these numbers started years before. Some are present permanently and some were there before I was even born - e.g., my home postal number is 43 (just as my shoe number). The pub I have been visiting most frequently is in the same street, on number 23. My son was born on 2003.11.23, etc. Note that numbers 22, 33 and 44 are all multiples of number 11, so perhaps number 11 is involved in these synchronicity events as well, although I do not see it (1×11) as often as these (2×11 , 3×11 , 4×11 , including 6×11 , which I may be encountering less often simply due to the fact that it is out of range of clocks and timestamps). Interestingly, regarding clocks and timestamps, 11 PM is equal to 23 h. And just the day before I started this experiment, the intensity of synchronicity was generally high. The day before the experiment started, on 2023.03.11 (note the number 11 here as well), I watched a documentary[2] titled "Collapse - based on the book by Jared Diamond" (2010). At some point during the movie I look at the clock (note that the last time I looked at the clock was hours ago), the clock was showing "23:22", I look back at the TV and it's showing a bunch of signs in a row with number 23 on them (it looked like a train station). The movie ends and the length of the movie shown at the player's bottom

catches my eye. It was 1:33:33. I close the player and I'm in Windows Explorer which is set up to show the details by default so it shows the modification date of files along with the name, type and size. It shows 2010.11.23 3:33 for the modification date of the movie filename (mkv).

Note that it appears the movie file was modified on my son's birthday (as noted, he was born 2003.11.23). Later I check where in the movie the scene with number 23 occurs - it's exactly 4 minutes and 33 seconds before the end.

Note also that this was the first time I've watched this movie, thus, all this synchronicity cannot be explained by subconscious measurement and action involving an internal biological clock, this one requires either effective local precognition on some subconscious level, or specific external coding or arrangement of synchronization of events by some *3rd party*. Both can be true to some degree.

In a different interpretation the internal clock is not involved, a 3rd party or some kind of temporal coding my mind is sensitive to may have induced synchronicity events by stimulating subconscious action at particular points in time.

Usually I avoid associating synchronicity with causality. However, in my theories, everything is completely relative. That includes causality, but also synchronicity. Thus, the arrangement/coding of synchronicity events probably exists and is observable in some reference frames. Our reference frame, however, is obviously very limited in that regard. Multiple interpretations are possible and multiple interpretations may be valid. One could even model synchronicity as a consequence of some force of attraction between entangled entities. It is clear, however, that this force is multidimensional and complex, and such forces are usually associated with living beings.

In that case, it seems that different levels (layers) of consciousness are differently susceptible to manipulation and that too is likely different between [sub]species - as animals (such as people) belonging to different subspecies have different subspecies of [sub]consciousness.

In any case, experience of synchronicity seems to be generally inversely proportional to the conscious action of the individual. This then explains why overwhelming synchronicity may be commonly *misinterpreted* as nervous breakdown - in these cases action is commonly delegated (or limited) to subconsciousness and subconsciousness may, with its effective knowledge of future, drive individuals towards experiences of synchronicity. This allows for the existence of prophets, however, regardless whether the 3rd party manipulation is

involved or not, accuracy of prediction is likely to depend on the individual [sub]consciousness, mostly on its [sub]species.

Prophecies of neutral[1] individuals are more likely to become true due to general lack of bias, although even in these, dates (timestamps) for the prediction may be misinterpreted by any consciousness they are communicated to, either due to different experience of time, inexperience, or lack of knowledge about the mechanism involved. In cases of overwhelming synchronicity significant amount of delusion certainly cannot be excluded (whether the cause is misinterpretation or not) in any case and the basis for the prediction has to be questioned. Predictions of neutral prophets probably should not be discarded *a priori* even in cases of overwhelming synchronicity but have to be confirmed independently by scientific method, at least as a possibility, preferably of a non-polarized mind, in a genuine attempt to reveal the truth.

6 Updates

6.1 2024.10.11

I'm still experiencing this clock synchronicity regularly, however, the amount of events per day (frequency of synchronicity[3]) generally fluctuated or oscillated about a stable mean. This has changed recently - the frequency has noticeably increased. The numbers with highest frequency are 23, 33 and 43. I suspect this is because I'm in another consciousness/body transformation event. Note that the age 44 has been found to be a transformational age in US[4]. Global average may be 43, or it may be the average for people of my species. I have reached 43 years of age just two months ago (on 2024.09.01). I have hypothesized elsewhere that, at least for those who experience it, synchronicity increases during transformation (strong evolution) events. And the amount of events seems to be proportional to the magnitude of transformation. Indeed, my biggest transformation peaked about the age of 36/37 when I was overwhelmed with synchronicity. I am detecting some changes in my body and behaviour now as well but this transformation is far from being as transformational as the previous one.

Is it a coincidence that this transformation is occurring at the age of 43? Not to me. This number, as the other two, is highly correlated with my life. As noted before, my home address number is 43 (this is where I was born and lived for most of my life, and that's where I currently live), my shoe number is 43, etc. It makes one wonder, do numbers 22/23, 33 and 43/44, all represent ages of transformation in people? Since synchronicity seems to increase during transformation, would it be surprising that the numbers themselves are highly correlated with transformation events?

Indeed, this seems to be the case for me. My child was born at my age of 22, this certainly was a transformational event. My marriage broke up 10 years later and I was divorced at the age of 33, this was a transformational event as well. In fact, I could interpret the age of 33 as the beginning of transformation

that reached its peak at the age of 36/37. The number 13 (also present in synchronicity events, but less often) is the average age of puberty (with both males and females included). It seems that these numbers represent beginnings/ends of cycles of transformation for animals of my species, with peaks somewhere in between - although, steep changes happen at the cycle beginnings/ends as well. When I think about it, I have been indeed learning and transforming whole my life. However, I haven't been experiencing much synchronicity - nor have I believed in it being anything more than meaningless coincidence, before the transformation that started at the age of 33 and peaked around 36/37. What changed? Well, exponential growth of my exploration, research, knowledge and awareness of the world and my self. Thus, even though synchronicity seems to be highly correlated with transformation, transformation alone is not enough for one to experience synchronicity. What is required seems to be an open, curious and neutral mind (but is that enough?). The amount of synchronicity experienced will then also be proportional to how open, how curious and how neutral the mind is. But this is again correlated with transformation. My mind has been very open, curious and neutral for years now and has been gradually transforming with acquired knowledge (day passing without me learning something insightful is a bad day for me) and that's probably why I have been experiencing synchronicity daily, and *vice versa* (some positive feedback certainly exists here).

7 Conclusion

In this particular experiment, synchronicity has been confirmed beyond 6σ level, effectively proving synchronicity is a real phenomenon. But proved to whom?

I did not do this experiment to prove synchronicity, my experience has proved it to me beyond any doubt, I just wanted to quantify some of it, see if any [additional] patterns (cycles) occur and see if I could learn more about it.

Note that I stopped this experiment at 9th *iteration*, not because synchronicity ended (quite contrary, *iteration* 10 was a peak too) but because I believe I've learned what was there to learn in this particular experiment.

As long as synchronicity remains a personal experience it probably will be considered as religious experience by the polarized academy. Evidence like the one above will hardly be accepted by those who lack trust. And lack of trust is not surprising in polarized society. But substantial trust is also required to experience substantial synchronicity - trust in one's self, especially deeper layers of self. Trust is essential for the translation of *mental* power into *physical* reality. If one's trust that a *cure* is a cure, can indeed cure one, what can be achieved by deeper trust in one's self and all the creatures it is bound with? The amount

of trust in one's self is often proportional to knowledge of one's self and this is why I recommend turning personal religion into personal science.

Once one genuinely realizes that its soul has layers, a *legion* of selves may become accessible for one to genuinely experience.

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